

NOVEL PRECURSOR MATERIALS AND APPROACHES FOR PRODUCING LOWER COST CARBON FIBER FOR HIGH VOLUME INDUSTRIES

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SUMMARY

Oak Ridge National Laboratory and FISIPE S.A. have developed a lower cost carbon fiber precursor based on textile grade, PAN fiber containing vinyl acetate. A chemical pretreatment of the textile grade material was developed and conversion conditions determined. This lower cost precursor is targeted to produce a new grade of carbon fiber for high volume industries.

Keywords: carbon fiber, precursor, conversion, module, integrate, validate, demonstrate, polyacrylonitrile

ABSTRACT

From easy to install bridges; to commercial aircraft; to ultra-lightweight fuel efficient vehicles, there has been great excitement about the potential for using carbon fiber reinforced composites during the last few years in high volume applications. Currently, the largest hurdle that inhibits wider implementation of carbon fiber composites in transportation, infrastructure and consumer goods industries is the high cost of carbon fiber when compared to other candidate materials. As part of the United State Department of Energy's (DOE) FreedomCAR initiative, significant research is being conducted to develop lower cost, high volume, technologies for producing carbon fiber. As a result of that work, new precursor materials and processing technologies have been developed which offer the potential for a future type of lower cost, moderate performance, high volume commodity grade of carbon fiber. This paper will highlight the on-going research and the potential future applications of less expensive fibers and discuss the development of an alternative precursor based upon polyacrylonitrile (PAN) fibers that contain vinyl acetate comonomer from high volume textile mills.

Through Department of Energy sponsorship, Oak Ridge National Laboratory and its partners have been developing technologies for the production of lower cost carbon fiber for use in body and chassis applications in automobiles. Program requirements target materials that have tensile strengths in excess of 1.73 GPa and modulus of at least 173 GPa but a cost of less than \$15.50 US per kilogram. That cost goal would allow the

introduction of carbon fiber based composites into a greater number of applications for future vehicles, windmills, bridge reinforcement, pressure vessels and other high volume industries. The technology pursued was the chemical modification of textile PAN containing either methyl acrylate or vinyl acetate as a co-monomer using a proprietary chemical bath while the fiber was still in the un-collapsed state in a typical wet-spinning operation. This was followed by a determination of the best concentration-temperature-exposure profiles to render the fiber rapidly oxidizable and subsequently carbonizable by conventional processes but also readily and inexpensively manufacturable in existing textile PAN plants. The time-temperature-tension profiles were then determined for converting the new precursor into carbon fiber. Currently strengths in excess of 2.50 GPA and moduli in excess of 220 GPA have been achieved.

Figure 1. Conventional Carbon Fiber Precursor (Front –Bottom)
Textile Based Carbon Fiber Precursor (Back – Top)

1. INTRODUCTION

The need to improve vehicle fuel efficiency is a major research priority in the United States, Europe and also in parts of Asia. The United States' transportation systems are 95% dependent on petroleum-based fuels. To supply this need, the United States imports roughly 55% of its petroleum requirements from abroad. To lessen dependence upon foreign sources, the National Energy Policy was developed and is administered by the United States Department of Energy (DOE). The National Energy Policy [1] calls for an aggressive agenda to reduce petroleum demand through energy efficiency while simultaneously increasing energy supply and diversifying the sources of energy used. The European Union is even more heavily dependent on imported oil, currently importing around 10 million barrels per day (bpd) to feed its 15 million bpd thirst. These figures make the European Union the second largest oil consumer in the world, after the United States [2]. The United Kingdom is, by far, the greatest oil-producing country within the European Union. Even so, since 1999, United Kingdom oil production has decreased steadily and since 2006, the United Kingdom became a net importer of oil, hence contributing to the European Union oil problem rather than helping it.

When environmental concerns, such as global warming from CO₂ emissions, are added to the equation, the problems of fuel efficiency (or lack thereof) become even more pressing. One of the ways in which fuel efficiency can be improved is by reducing the *weight of vehicles*. In turn, this can be achieved by the use of lighter weight alloys (e.g.

aluminum, magnesium) or polymer-matrix composites in place of the more traditional steel. This represents the area of focus of this paper – specifically in the development of low-cost carbon fiber materials destined for automotive applications.

United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) data for light vehicles between 1980 and 2004 suggest that in this period, there were dramatic improvements in automobile technology which should have lead to higher fuel efficiencies. However, the problem has been that consumer demands dictated making the cars larger and better performing rather than in reducing fuel consumption. Original equipment manufacturers' (OEMs) objectives for safety, coupled with customer demands for space, performance, extra features, and minimal noise, vibration and harshness (NVH) have caused the average light-duty vehicle weight to increase each year since 1987 (Figure 2A). OEMs also developed vehicles with increased performance, as indicated by 0-97 kilometers per hours (0-60 mph) time reductions, during that same time period [3].

As a result of more luxurious consumer demands and increased vehicle performance, gains from technological advances in fuel efficient vehicles during this period have been largely negated by the increased fuel consumption of heavier cars. Meanwhile, automotive OEMs have been able to maintain corporate average fuel economy nearly constant (Figure 2B). Maintaining level fuel economy while increasing the 0-97 kilometers per hour performance of heavier and heavier vehicles has been a monumental challenge that the industry has done well to achieve. This, however, is not a sustainable situation and current research is directed towards a longer-term solution. [3]

Figure 2A. [3]

Average Vehicle Weight and

Figure 2B. [3]

Average Vehicle Fuel Economy

Historically, automotive technology has been a concern of the U.S. Government since the environmental movement of the 1960s and the oil crisis of the 1970s. During those decades, the Clean Air Acts established standards for emissions [4]. The Energy Policy and Conservation Act of 1975 [5] established corporate average fuel economy standards for light duty vehicles. During the 1970s and 1980s, significant research was conducted by both government and private industry aimed primarily at increasing fuel efficiency

while simultaneously reducing emissions. Most research was centered on propulsion systems, fuels and their associated efficiencies. In 1994 the Partnership for a New Generation of Vehicles (PNGV) was formed between government and industry to develop advanced vehicle technologies. PNGV was a co-operative partnership between several departments of the federal government and the United States Council for Automotive Research (USCAR). That program represented a significant paradigm shift. Government and the automotive industry formed a true working relationship with environmental, economic and business goals being pursued in the laboratory through joint technology development rather than dictated by regulation. This form of co-operative research has been extended to the FreedomCAR initiative.

The reduction in curb weight can only be obtained by replacing many of the structural materials in a vehicle with alternative, lighter weight structural materials or materials that allow the use of significantly thinner parts. Candidate materials for mass reduction are shown below in Table 1 [6] along with cost impediments to their implementation. Introduction of fuel cell powered vehicles will also require significant mass reductions due to the weight of the propulsion system along with the lower power densities upon introduction, as compared to more efficient systems that will be developed in later years.

Composite materials research for body and chassis systems is conducted jointly between the DOE and the Automotive Composites Consortium (ACC), which is one of several cooperative, pre-competitive research consortia, under the United States Council for Automotive Research (USCAR), formed by Ford Motor Company, General Motors Corporation and Chrysler Corporation. The ACC's charter is to develop structural and semi-structural composite materials for body and chassis applications (since this is where the greatest weight of the vehicle is, and hence where the greatest potential for weight reduction exists). Currently a significant portion of the ACC/DOE research portfolio is dedicated to developing carbon fiber composites. Since the largest impediment to incorporation of carbon fiber composites is the high cost of the carbon fiber, significant resources are dedicated to developing the technologies necessary to produce a lower cost carbon fiber by developing lower cost precursors and more efficient precursor conversion technologies.

Table 1. Candidate Lightweighting Alternative Materials [6]

		Critical Challenges				
		Low-cost fibers	High-volume Mfg.	Recycling	Joining	Predictive Modeling
Increasing Impact on Mission	Carbon-fiber Composites	Feedstock Cost	Manufac-ing	Improved Alloys	Recycling	
	Aluminum	Feedstock Cost	Improved Alloys	Corrosion Protection	Manufac-ing	Recycling
	Magnesium	Feedstock Cost	Improved Alloys	Corrosion Protection	Manufac-ing	Recycling
	Advanced High-strength Steels	Manufacturability	Wt. Red. Concepts	Alloy Development		
	Titanium	Low-cost Extraction	Low-cost Production	Forming & Machining	Low-cost PM	Alloy Development
	Metal-matrix Composites	Feedstock Cost	Compositing Methods	Powder Handling	Compaction	Machining & Forming
	Glazings	Low-cost Lightweight Matls.	Noise, T ^o struc. models simulations	Noise reduction techniques	UV and IR blockers	
	Emerging Materials and Manufacturing	Material Cost	Mfg-ability	Design Concepts	Performance Models	

Chart is provided courtesy of Robert McCune - Ford Motor Company

2. BACKGROUND

Early implementation of carbon fiber in the automotive industry started in the 1970s. The automotive industry, together with suppliers and composite manufacturers, was able to demonstrate that carbon fiber based composites, when properly designed, can become a sound integral component of an automobile. Today, most of the carbon fiber composite applications in the automotive industry can be found in expensive, low production rate, models. Carbon fiber is often used in components as a recognizable high end upgrade for the luxury vehicle market. Recent applications can be found in deck lids and seats (Ford GT); fenders, wheel house and floor pan (Chevrolet Corvette); fenders, doors and windshield surrounds (Dodge Viper); carbon fiber roof (BMW M3); transmission tunnel, “A” pillar and frontal crash structures (Aston Martin Vanquish); and even carbon fiber intensive vehicles designs such as the Mercedes McLaren. Common to all these applications are the low volumes and high costs of the vehicles. The current carbon fiber market cannot support either the cost requirements or the volume requirements of high volume vehicle platforms.

Current global carbon fiber production capacity is slightly above 48 million kilograms (106 million pounds) per year (Figure 3) [7] with major expansions in capacity announced by most of the carbon fiber producers. Current global vehicle production is 60-65 million vehicles per year. Current carbon fiber capacity could only supply 2/3 kilogram (1.5 pounds) of fiber for each vehicle if the automotive industry were the only user of carbon fiber. To achieve the required industry scale-up will require changes to carbon fiber production technologies, production facilities, packaging, emission control procedures and likely even changes in the precursors used to manufacture carbon fiber. That increase in capacity will not only need to meet the needs of the automotive industry but also the needs of many other industries having similar requirements that would grow as a result of automotive industry penetration, material cost requirements and experience.

Figure 3. Current Global Carbon Fiber Capacity [7]

Carbon fiber is typically made by highly controlled thermal pyrolysis of only a few types of precursors. This naturally begs the question: Are these the only materials, energy methods and production technologies capable of producing carbon fiber? In response to this, DOE has developed and coordinated with the ACC, a research portfolio aimed at reducing the cost of carbon fibers. The current research portfolio includes the development of:

- i. non-traditional precursors;
- ii. novel fiber production methods;
- iii. means for fully developing these advances in a demonstration user facility which will be available to potential suppliers.

The synergistic effects of improving both precursor and manufacturing costs may bring carbon fiber costs within acceptable ranges for the automotive industry. DOE cost goals as coordinated with the ACC are to reduce carbon fiber costs to a range of US\$11.00-15.40 per kilogram (US\$5 - US\$7 per pound). Costs within or approaching that range would also have a significant impact on wind power, oil and gas, construction, power transmission and a variety of other industries.

As more aggressive DOE weight reduction goals were defined, it became apparent that carbon fiber-based composites were serious candidates for enabling those goals to be met. Carbon fiber-based composites are restricted in automotive industry use due to the high current cost of carbon fiber in comparison to other potential vehicle structural materials. The greatest cost factors in carbon fiber production are the high cost of precursors (45-60% of production costs) and the high capital equipment costs (20-35% of production costs) [8].

3. COST MODELS

In 2007, the ACC funded a cost study by Kline and Co. to evaluate the effectiveness of the DOE carbon fiber research portfolio and to aid in determining future research directions. As part of the modeling tasks, a baseline cost model of current carbon fiber manufacturing costs (Figure 4) [8] was created. The cost model indicates a production cost of roughly US\$20.90 per kilogram (US\$9.60 per pound) produced on conventional 900 metric ton (two million pound) per year lines. If the line size were scaled-up for higher volume production, at around 4.51 million kilograms (10 million pounds) per year, the point of diminishing returns would be reached. At that point the carbon fiber cost would be around US\$17.35 per kilogram (US\$7.88 per pound). Since the DOE is program is aimed at high volume production capabilities, this figure was used as the baseline against which all potential technologies were evaluated.

Figure 4. Cost vs Annual Volume for Conventional Carbon Fiber Processing [8]

The cost model showed that precursor costs account for just over half the cost of manufacturing carbon fiber (Figure 5) [8]. Since polyacrylonitrile is a petroleum based product, the precursor cost is continuing to fluctuate with crude oil prices and the resultant cost in manufacturing carbon fiber is likewise fluctuating. Simultaneously, the value of lightweighting and increasing fuel efficiency is also varying with crude oil prices. With precursor costs accounting for such a large percentage of the total manufacturing costs, changing the precursor used to manufacture carbon fiber has the most significant impact on reducing the final fiber cost. Previous collaborative work with the ACC has shown that typical carbon fiber properties (modulus > 207 GPA) may not be needed for many automotive components. In high volume manufacturing of automotive parts, there are practical limits as to how thin parts may be designed and processed while still holding tolerances over fairly large surface areas. Design studies have shown that 172 GPA (25 MSI) modulus and 1.72 GPA (250 KSI) strength fibers offer sufficient properties to mold as thin a part as is practical for the majority of automotive components. This is particularly true where stiffness and not strength is the primary limiting design parameter. *Due to the reduced fiber property requirements, several new precursors and processing technologies became available for program consideration that would not have been available if property requirements were higher.*

Figure 5. Cost Elements in Carbon Fiber Manufacture and % of Cost Portion. [8]

As a result, two types of non-traditional carbon fiber precursors are being examined in the DOE program. *Hardwood and softwood lignins* were first evaluated in Japan in the 1960's and 1970's. [9] Oak Ridge National Laboratory and Pacific Northwest National Laboratory have continued that work in recent years to further develop lignin precursors. Hardwood and softwood lignins showed the most significant potential for cost reduction but also have a much larger degree of scientific uncertainty and program risk associated with them. The initial development of *textile PAN-based precursors* was conducted by Hexcel [10] using fiber supplied by Sterling in Pensacola, Florida. More recently, ORNL has been developing textile based precursors with FISIFE S.A. in Lisbon, Portugal. According to the cost model

(Figure 6), textile based precursors showed the potential to reduce carbon fiber cost by more than US\$4.40 per kilogram due to the high volume nature of the textile industry and the higher oxygen content of the resultant precursor yielding reduced oxidation times. The textile precursors also have a substantially reduced program risk when compared to lignin-based precursors, due to similarities in processing PAN-based textile precursors and conventional PAN-based carbon fiber precursors, making them easier to incorporate into current production facilities. Currently, two different precursors have been developed.

Figure 6. Carbon Fiber Costs Using Alternative Precursors and Conventional Processing [CF: Conventional Precursor; TEX: Textile Precursor; HKL: Hardwood Lignin; SKL: Softwood Lignin] [8]

In addition to the development of alternative precursors, ORNL has three programs to develop alternative processing technologies. One program has developed a Microwave Assisted Plasma (MAP) technology which would replace the low and high temperature carbonization ovens in conventional processing of current lower cost carbon fibers. A second program (Advanced Stabilization) would replace the first of four oxidative stabilization ovens in the process and the third project (Advanced Oxidation) would replace the final three ovens used in conventional processing. Each of these technologies has demonstrated a significant reduction in residence time. Using a precursor that conventionally requires 90 – 120 minutes of residence time in thermal oxidative stabilization ovens, the advanced modules have accomplished the same job in less than 35 minutes. The cost model combined potential cost savings of using alternative precursors with alternative processing methods to develop the potential synergistic cost chart shown in Figure 7, which combines all technologies being developed. Program plans are to develop alternative precursors, initially for conventional processing (Figure 6) as the lowest risk path for incorporation into current and future carbon fiber manufacturing facilities. The development of the textile precursors is nearing completion and will soon be available from FISIFE. Lignin precursors will require a longer development cycle but could be a significant product from bio-refineries which produce ethanol for fuel.

Initial development of advanced processing technologies is being conducted with conventional carbon fiber precursors. Once these technologies are sufficiently scaled, advanced precursors will then be incorporated to achieve the ultimate savings shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Carbon Fiber Costs: Alternative Precursors and Alternative Processing [8]

4. TEXTILE BASED PRECURSORS

As discussed earlier in the section on cost modeling of carbon fibers, precursor cost is approximately 50% of the total carbon fiber manufacturing cost. Therefore, a lower cost precursor is required to reduce the final carbon fiber cost. Specialty PAN-based precursors that are used for producing aerospace-grade carbon fibers are very high-quality proprietary fibers and production of such fibers requires precise control on polymer composition, purity, molecular weight distribution and molecular orientation in the fibers. Retention of specific fiber morphological characteristics during early conversion steps including steam stretching, preheating and oxidative stabilization is also very critical to obtain desired properties of the resultant fibers. Due to the difference between aerospace and automotive material property requirements, precursor quality and carbon fiber performance can be traded-off with cost. PAN-based acrylic textiles are lower-cost, higher volume fibers compared to the aerospace and commercial specialty PAN-based carbon fiber precursors.

Previously, under a separate contract as part of the Automotive Lightweighting Materials (ALM) program, Hexcel Corporation developed the basic science necessary to render textile-based PAN polymers carbonizable. Dasarathy and coworkers demonstrated the proof-of-concept that textile PAN fibers can be successfully converted into carbon fibers with properties that can surpass the program goal of 1.72 GPA tensile strength, 172 GPA modulus and 1% ultimate elongation. [11] As-spun textile PAN fibers are not readily processable into carbon fiber. A chemical modification protocol was developed for textile fiber. During textile fiber spinning, the material is subjected to a low cost chemical pretreatment which renders the textile fiber suitable for conventional oxidative stabilization and subsequent carbonization. [12, 13]

Figure 8. DSC thermograms of representative fiber samples in air. Scans were done at 20°C/min using TA Instruments' Q1000 DSC equipment.

Under the FreedomCAR initiative of DOE, low-cost carbon fibers are being produced at ORNL from chemically modified textile PAN fibers in collaboration with FISIFE S. A.. Fibers are produced and chemically pretreated in Portugal at the FISIFE facilities, and then sent to ORNL for evaluation, oxidative stabilization and carbonization. In the early stages of the project, many different generations of textile precursor tows were produced using various chemical pretreatments, characterized, and converted into carbonized fibers. The degree of in-line chemical modification during precursor fiber spinning was characterized in terms of the rate of exothermic reaction that usually occurs with PAN based fibers during oxidative stabilization. Figure 8 displays DSC thermograms of different types of PAN based precursors. It is apparent that specialty PAN fibers (aerospace grade precursor) exhibit a sharp exotherm at temperatures ranging from 225°C to 325°C. On the other hand, virgin textile based PAN fibers exhibit exothermic reactions at relatively higher temperatures ranging from 275°C to 360°C. Chemical treatment of fibers significantly lowers the on-set temperature of the exothermic reaction and accelerates the oxidative stabilization. This chemical pretreatment produces a “left shift” of the DSC thermograph making the conventional thermal process more suitable for its oxidation and thus conversion into carbon fiber.

The first step in development of the precursor was to evaluate the DSC curves of more than 30 potential formulations that FISIFE made with a variety of proprietary additives. The onset of the exotherms, seen in the DSC curves, is indicative of the onset of stabilization and the steepness of the curves and is indicative of the severity of the exotherm during oxidative stabilization. Less steep curves indicate a less severe exotherm which correspondingly could result in more rapid stabilization.

Once candidate precursors were selected, FISIFE installed a chemical treatment unit in their pilot line and began generating chemically pretreated samples. ORNL has conducted extensive characterization of chemically modified precursors and polymer

Figure 9. Processing of FISIFE precursor using ORNL's precursor evaluation line.

samples generated by FISIFE, as well as conversion trials on filaments and tows generated by FISIFE from selected precursor chemical compositions. By the end of FY2007, FISIFE was making multiple spools of chemically treated 26.6K tow at 2 – 3 kg of fiber per spool. This fiber has subsequently been used for conversion trials in ORNL's precursor evaluation system and pilot line where the time-temperature-tension protocols were then developed to oxidize, stabilize and carbonize different batches of chemically-modified, PAN-based textile fibers.

The first step in determining the conversion protocol was to determine oxidation temperatures to obtain optimal processing conditions. This was done using the precursor evaluation line and measuring the oxidation density while targeting values that would be close to conventional carbon fiber precursors that were fully oxidized. Oxidized densities slightly higher than industrial grade precursors and slightly lower than aerospace grade precursors have been obtained.

Subsequently, ORNL has been using both the precursor evaluation line and the pilot line to determine time-temperature-tension processing profiles for the FISIFE precursor. Program requirements are to develop fibers with strengths of 250 KSI and moduli of 25 MSI. Figures 10A and 10B, respectively, show the evolution of the strength and modulus during development of processing conditions over time. We have currently reached strengths of 363 KSI which exceeds program goals and are also well above program goals on modulus with a current value of 31.7 MSI. The addition of differential tensioning during upgrade of the pilot line should yield significant improvement in the mechanical properties.

Figure 10A. Obtained strength (KSI) of carbon fiber produced from FISIFE precursor during development of the processing protocol as a function of time.

Figure 10B. Obtained modulus (MSI) of carbon fiber produced from FISIFE precursor during development of the processing protocol as a function of time.

At the end of FY2008, ORNL delivered spools of fully carbonized textile precursor based carbon fiber to Ford, General Motors and Chrysler meeting the program milestone and property requirements. The single-filament mechanical properties of carbonized fibers are summarized in Table 2. Carbonized fibers of diameter exceeding program goals were obtained. Tow property measurements of 26K filament tows were made, and tow properties of 200-228 GPA modulus and 2.14-2.69 GPA strength have been obtained.

Figure 11. Carbon fibers produced from FISIFE precursor.

Table 2: Single filament tensile properties of different carbonized fibers obtained from textile PAN precursors.

Textile Fiber Spools	Diameter (mm)	Tensile strength (GPA)	Tensile modulus (GPA)	Elongation (%)
Batch I	6-7	2.10-2.96	145-204	1.0-1.6
Batch II	6-7	1.59-2.41	136-205	0.7-1.5
Batch III	6-7	2.07-2.76	152-201	1.0-1.6
Batch IV	6-7	2.07-2.93	165-235	0.8-1.6
Batch V	6-7	1.72-2.41	141-200	0.8-1.4
Minimum Program Goals	6-7	1.72	172	>1%

5. ADVANCED STABILIZATION AND OXIDATION

The purpose of this portion of the program is to investigate and develop a plasma processing technique to rapidly and inexpensively oxidize PAN precursor fibers. Conventional oxidation is a slow thermal process that typically consumes over 80% of the processing time in a conventional carbon fiber conversion line depending upon the precursor chemistry and processing recipe. A rapid oxidation process could dramatically increase the conversion line throughput and appreciably lower the fiber cost. A related project has already demonstrated the potential for greatly increasing line speed in the carbonization and graphitization stages, and rapid stabilization techniques are being developed, but the oxidation time must be greatly reduced to effect fast conversion. This

work intends to develop advanced plasma oxidation technology that integrates with other advanced fiber conversion processes to produce inexpensive carbon fiber with properties suitable for use by the automotive industry. This methodology should produce fiber that meets critical technical criteria such as uniform properties over the length of the fiber tow; repeatable and controllable processing; and significant unit cost reduction compared with conventional processing.

Conversion of polymeric precursor fibers to finished carbon fibers is time-consuming, energy intensive, and a significant contributor to the production cost of carbon fibers. Diffusive thermal oxidation is the rate-limiting steps in the conventional carbon fiber conversion process. PAN stabilization and oxidation occur in successive furnaces in air, at temperatures increasing from about 200 to 270°C. ORNL is developing techniques for dramatically accelerating the stabilization and oxidation steps to reduce carbon fiber conversion cost. The team has previously demonstrated the feasibility of using atmospheric plasma-based processing to oxidize polyacrylonitrile precursor fibers more rapidly than can be done by conventional oxidation.

Figure 12. Early generation plasma conversion reactor.

Exposure to plasma products at or near atmospheric pressure provides superior thermal control because the gas flow convectively heats or cools the fibers. This is deemed particularly important to avoid fiber melting or interfilamentary welding from exothermic reactions. However, the short mean free path and life span of the chemically reactive species at atmospheric pressure presents another set of challenges, principally associated with finding a process recipe that delivers high process stability and short residence times. Figure 12 shows an early generation plasma reactor. Significant equipment and process modifications were made on a continuous basis to improve performance. The reactor system has been redesigned and reconfigured many times for higher volume and more rapid oxidation with better controllability and enhanced performance.

Plasma oxidation of PAN fibers continues to progress toward the goal of reducing the cost of carbon fiber manufacture. To date, the researchers have reduced oxidation residence time by about 3X compared to conventional oxidation (using an aerospace type PAN precursor), achieved 0.3 m/min line speed in a six-zone, multi-pass reactor configuration, and demonstrated four hours of continuous reactor operation. Plasma oxidized fibers were carbonized and the mechanical properties checked, with moderate to good results considering the current stage of process development.

Table 3. Residence Time Requirements for Advance Oxidation and Stabilization Routes.

Stabilization Method	Time Required	Thermal Post Treatment	Advanced Oxidation	Total Time
E-Beam	Seconds	20-26 Min	20-24 Min	40-50 Min
Ultraviolet	6-7 Min	None	20-24 Min	26-31 Min
ThermoChemical	5-10 Min	None	20-24 Min	25-34 Min
Conventional	100-120 Min			100-120 Min

6. MICROWAVE-ASSISTED PLASMA CARBONIZATION

This part of the project is based upon a discovery that microwave energy could potentially be used as a means to rapidly convert polyacrylonitrile (PAN) precursor fibers into finished carbon fibers. It was determined that the best approach was to use a combination of microwaves and plasma, or microwave-assisted plasma (MAP), to carbonize and graphitize oxidized PAN fibers. MAP processing feasibility was demonstrated in a batch reactor during the early stages of this work. Continuous operation was then demonstrated in a low-speed single-tow reactor, which was subsequently scaled to achieve high-speed single-tow operation, and finally three-tow operation. A residence time approximately 1/3 of the conventional residence time was achieved. This resulted in a single-tow line speed approximately 5 m/min, with a reactor length roughly 40% of a conventional furnace's length. Based on energy profile measurements, it appears that a further 2X or more reduction of the residence time should be possible. The final project demonstration was MAP carbonization and graphitization of three 50k tows at 1 m/min, operating continuously for one hour. The MAP process, when operated within system design parameters, has consistently produced fibers that exceeded the fiber property targets.

Figure 13. Microwave Assisted Plasma Multi-Tow Experimental Unit.

For carbonization and graphitization of large tow (>48k), commercial grade carbon fiber, MAP process advantages over the conventional thermal process include:

- Shorter residence time;
- Higher line speeds and/or smaller equipment footprint;
- Reduced unit capital investment;
- Reduced unit energy demand;
- Lower temperature operation;
- Parametrically highly tunable;
- Significantly lower/reduced thermal inertia of the overall system.
- Very fast turnaround for maintenance, repair, and production cycle set-up (equipment start-up and shutdown cycle in 20 – 60 minutes vs. 12 – 40 hours);
- Reduced hazardous effluents and/or emission treatment requirements; and
- Inherently controllable surface chemistry, resulting in improved composite properties. (An acceptable level of surface treatment can be generated in situ on the MAP processed fibers.

The Kline cost model [8] estimated that the MAP process could reduce carbon fiber production cost by about 10% – 20%, depending on plant size, operational assumptions, and level of detail in the model. This is generally a reduction of almost 50% in the cost of the carbonization and graphitization steps that are accomplished by the MAP process.

7. FUTURE RESEARCH

Future research in the Low Cost Carbon Fiber initiative will focus largely on continued investigation of alternative precursors, scale-up, integration of the precursors and conversion processes under development, surface engineering for compatibility with selected resins, and implementation in downstream manufacturing processes.

In addition to textile PAN and lignin, other precursor candidates may be of interest in the future. PAN and lignin are both handicapped by relatively low yield. Lignin precursors have a somewhat complicated chemistry which may present issues with both spinning into a precursor and subsequent conversion into carbon fiber. Hence a precursor with low raw material cost and high yield, which could be inexpensively converted into competent fiber, would be of great interest. Polyolefins are the least expensive petrochemicals and offer high yield, but to date no one has developed an acceptable conversion process for polyolefin fibers. Hexcel concluded in its Low Cost Carbon Fiber project that linear low density polyethylene has high potential as a low cost precursor, [10, 11, 12] but chose to pursue textile PAN because it could be developed much more rapidly and with less investment. Thus polyolefins are a potential area of future precursor research. Other new and novel precursors would also be of interest.

Scale-up of all precursor and conversion technology remains one of the major challenges and future thrusts within this program. At this time, only the textile PAN precursor is closer to a scale needed for commercialization. Melt-spun lignin-based precursor is currently at the scale of tens or hundreds of filaments; advanced stabilization and

oxidation are at the scale of a single small tow with line speed < 1 m/min, and microwave-assisted carbonization is at the scale of three large tows with line speed ~ 1 m/min. We expect that commercial implementation will be at scales of tens of large ($>50k$) tows with line speeds ≥ 100 m/min in precursor manufacturing, and tens of large tows with line speeds on the order of 10 m/min for conversion. ORNL plans to demonstrate a scale of at least five large tows, with residence times that enable the above line speeds in footprints no larger than that of today's conventional factories.

As this effort progresses, an integration of these advanced technologies into the fiber production process has to be implemented. Technological integration will be undertaken in a modular manner using a well characterized pilot line, using a well evaluated precursor. A selected single conventional processing step will be replaced by one of these advanced technologies, so that the resultant carbon fiber can be analyzed to evaluate the impact of the new technological module on the final carbon fiber properties.

Surface engineering for compatibility with selected resins is another important area of future research. Plasma surface treatment is a well-known surface activation technique. ORNL's plasma-based processes produce inherently active surfaces that can be tailored for the intended resin without damaging the fiber surface. To date, we have observed this phenomenon but have done little work to develop, understand, and control a robust plasma surface treatment method. Furthermore, most available sizing technology is targeted to epoxy resins due to their extensive use with aerospace grade fibers. ORNL plans to create strategic partnerships that will develop surface treatment and sizing technology that are highly compatible with commodity resins, specifically including vinyl esters, polyesters, and polyurethanes. A new project will be established soon to tackle the issues of surface treatments for commodity, low cost, carbon fibers for use in low cost resin matrix systems such as vinyl esters.

Finally, it is important to ensure that ORNL's low cost carbon fibers can be formatted and used in downstream manufacturing processes. Therefore, we plan to work with strategic partners to develop appropriate formatting techniques and demonstrate that low cost carbon fibers can be successfully used in robust manufacturing processes. While fiber manufacturing economics drive commercial grade fiber manufacturers to large tow production, best structural properties require small tow. [14] Therefore tow splitting will be required somewhere in the fiber manufacturing and use value chain. ORNL is working on the development of robotic preforming using commercially available carbon fibers or mixtures of carbon and glass fibers, and eventually this project will be supplied with fibers from the LCCF initiative. One of the most compelling opportunities is carbon fiber sheet molded compound (CF-SMC). Over half of today's automotive composites are glass reinforced SMC, including both structural and Class A surfaces, and comprising a large volume of existing composite applications. CF-SMC would be essentially a "drop-in" replacement for conventional SMC, thus it is likely to be accepted much more readily than composites that are replacing primary metal structures. The major challenge is fiber cost. CF-SMC is currently being developed by the automotive industry. ORNL expects to partner with SMC manufacturers and end users to demonstrate the use of its low cost carbon fiber in CF-SMC. ORNL also plans to evaluate other opportunities to demonstrate the use of low cost carbon fiber in downstream formatting and manufacturing processes.

8. CONCLUSIONS

Significant advances have been made in the United States through joint government-industry research toward developing lower cost carbon fiber for high volume applications with particular interest in a lower cost carbon fiber for automotive applications. New precursors based upon textile grade polyacrylonitrile have been developed and lignin based precursors are well on their way to being ready for future composite systems. Advanced processing technologies are being developed. The program is beginning multiple efforts to commercialize these technologies with partners that cannot be publically disclosed at this time. Efforts are underway to develop material forms and composite material systems based upon these lower cost technologies. Significant interest is being generated to use these new materials in wind power, automotive, oil and gas, power transmission and infrastructure applications. All of this is geared toward reducing our dependence on foreign oil, minimizing the environmental impact of the automobile, and improving our economy.

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